

DARE UK

DARE UK aims to design and deliver a coordinated and trustworthy national data research infrastructure to support cross-domain research for public good.

Phase 1 Driver Projects Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Report

Contents

Background

Phase 1 Driver Projects

With funding from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) - the UK's largest public funder of research and innovation - DARE UK awarded over £2 million to five Driver Projects to address some of the challenges researchers face in conducting sensitive data research in the UK.

Data security – with the major overarching concern being data security – how do we make sure data used for research is kept safely and de-identified?

Data linking – how do we connect data between different research centres/organisations and data managers/custodians?

Data access – how can we safely access data between different research centres/organisations?

Data access in the UK fundamentally needs to change in order for research and outputs to improve.

Professor Simon Thompson, Swansea University, TELEPORT Principal Investigator (PI)

The five Driver Projects aimed to address the accessibility, linkage, and safety concerns around the use of personal data, while reinforcing public trust in the systems that govern data research.

Background

Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

The way sensitive data research is currently conducted involves the use of TREs. **TREs are secure spaces for researchers to access and analyse sensitive data.** They help prevent unauthorised access and/or re-identification of individuals from de-identified data.

Although researchers may be familiar with TREs and how they operate, TREs are not always structured and managed in the same way. Different TREs across the UK follow different standards and processes and it is difficult for researchers to link and analyse data from different TREs.

The DARE UK Driver Projects explored solutions for more standardised approaches to designing and running TREs, so that **data can be more easily analysed across TREs in a safe, secure, and efficient way.**

Phase 1 of the Driver Projects has now been completed, and each of the five projects sought ways to increase the usability, access, interconnectivity, and safety of TREs.

Jargon buster

What is a TRE?

TREs are highly secure computing environments that provide remote access to sensitive data for approved research that can save and improve lives.

What are the benefits of a TRE?

TREs help make research safe, secure and trustworthy, helping trusted researchers make important discoveries.

Why are TREs important?

Making data available through a TRE means people can be confident that their personal data is accessed securely and their privacy is protected.

What is data de-identification?

The removal of 'identifiers' such as name or address from personal data so that the data can be used anonymously.

Background

Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE)

Central to all Driver Projects has been involvement and engagement with the public. Across all Driver Projects, members of the public participated in workshops, joined project teams, and contributed to surveys, generating insights, ideas, and input which has been central to each project and the overall DARE UK vision.

People have an awful lot of concerns around what's happening with their data – around who's using it, for what, or is it being sold? For all sorts of data research, we rely on public trust. And when we don't have that trust, we don't get the data. And without that data, we build schools in the wrong place, we build roads in the wrong place – we can't plan for what the country needs to look like.

**Professor Jim Smith, University of the West of England,
SACRO Principal Investigator (PI)**

SARA:

Semi-Automated Risk Assessment of Data Provenance and Clinical Free-Text in TREs

Semi-Automated Risk Assessment of Data Provenance and Clinical Free-Text was a collaboration involving the University of Edinburgh, University of Aberdeen, West of Scotland Safe Haven, University of Sussex, and Public Health Scotland.

01: SARA - Project overview and PIE activities

SARA: Semi-Automated Risk Assessment Of Data Provenance And Clinical Free-Text In TREs

This project aimed to address concerns around risk assessment at two key stages - data production and data access by researchers. The team focused on two areas:

- **Data provenance** – how we track data preparation in a TRE to make them ready for research.
- **Free-text, unstructured data** – data that typically doesn't get released because of inherent privacy risks, with the aim to get value from these data by running a risk assessment and creating a pathway for faster researcher access.

In a nutshell, the SARA project aimed to enhance the value from these data by better understanding possible risks and building mitigations for these risks, to ultimately enable faster research access without compromising security or confidentiality.

“We want to involve public perspectives in what we are doing to support health and social care. We need to get a sense from members of the public of the acceptable ‘limits’ of data sharing and the use of semi-automation in preparing data for research.”

Stuart Dunbar, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

01: SARA - Project overview and PIE activities

Overview

Good quality research often needs data to be sourced across different health systems; this process is time-consuming and poses risks such as individuals being identified (either directly or indirectly). The SARA team's work aimed to support decision-making and overcome risks when working with health data, while ensuring time-efficiency for researchers.

There is potential to enhance the systems currently used by data service teams. More robust options could speed up checks on core aspects of the risk assessment process, as well as highlight areas where analysts and information governance experts should focus their attention. **This can be achieved with semi-automated processes that can be incorporated by a range of teams who handle health data on a day-to-day basis,** including data analysts, researchers, and information governance teams.

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What we've done at the SARA project matters. We want research to be innovative and we want to be able to improve the data-access pathways that support research. So, if we can both speed up the process, in terms of data access, but also be able to share with the researchers how we do that data linkage, it helps researchers build better models, which has the potential to turn into solutions with real-world impact.

Dr Arlene Casey, Principal Investigator (PI)

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01: SARA - Project overview and PIE activities

Listening to public opinion

Like all DARE UK funded projects, the SARA project engaged with the public via a set of PIE activities.

The purpose of these activities was to include public perspectives on risk assessment within health data research, to inform approaches to understanding privacy risks and the later design of preventative tools. The project team accomplished this in close collaboration with [Ipsos Scotland](#), by designing discussion-based workshops and a survey with a representative sample of adults in Scotland.

Workshops – two in-person workshops, delivered over two half-days, were hosted in different locations in Scotland – Edinburgh (including 22 participants), and Aberdeen (including 17 participants). Before the workshops, participants attended a half-day online introduction, where they explored perspectives around risk assessment and semi-automation within health data research. As part of the development of these workshops, the SARA team designed case study and scenario materials to support discussion.

Survey – the survey was informed by the initial findings of the workshops and aimed to seek broader perspectives on key themes through Ipsos's UK KnowledgePanel. Through this approach, SARA reached a representative sample of 1,030 adults in Scotland.

The inclusion of our survey questions through the UK KnowledgePanel enabled us to reach a genuinely representative sample of the adult population in Scotland. We would not have achieved this diversity, nor magnitude, if we attempted to promote the survey through our own channels.

SARA Team

01: SARA - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - process

The PIE activities surfaced the following key learnings:

 Technical terminology – TRE risk-assessment and TRE risk mitigation were important technical terms to discuss with the public. Despite being common language within the team, explaining them to the public was key in getting participants comfortable with discussing them.

 Demographic targets – a particular challenge for the team was achieving the demographic targets, especially level of education. Engaging those with no formal qualifications was difficult, perhaps due to the technical nature of the topics to be discussed.

Ipsos Scotland mitigated this by including more participants from other educational levels. Withdrawals from the Aberdeen workshop were mitigated by Ipsos Scotland having a reserve list in place. These practical responses from Ipsos Scotland were highly valued.

 Consent – the notion of consent in the use of data was frequently discussed in the context of the SARA project. When consent was mentioned, the Ipsos Scotland facilitators expertly recognised the concerns and directed participants back to the topic at hand in a sensitive and positive way. This was a particularly important intervention – had this been mishandled, participants may have felt unheard and may have withdrawn from the discussions.

PIE learnings - impacts on the project

The PIE activities surfaced the following key learnings which have directly impacted the overall project:

Semi-automation is acceptable provided a sensible 'human' check remains:

- Fundamentally, the use of semi-automation was deemed acceptable (acknowledging the benefits of scale and speed) as long as there is human involvement to interpret the nuances and make key decisions.

The privacy of individuals and their health data needs to be balanced against the usefulness of these data:

- Actions are needed to protect patient privacy when making data available for research. However, there were also concerns around removing too much information, as this would negatively impact the quality and usefulness of the research.

Transparency and recording of decision-making is essential:

- To ensure a transparent data provenance process, participants recommended having a decision log as part of record-keeping dashboards, including decisions made about data included or excluded (and why). For maintaining confidentiality, participants recommended clear communication between researchers and TRE analysts to make decisions that balance patient privacy with relevance to the research.

The outcomes of the public consultation work have been invaluable for the decisions made in the development of the approaches to understanding privacy risk and prototype dashboards by the team.

SARA Team

The computer is very black and white and you need the human to catch the greys in between.

Public Participant

01: SARA - Project overview and PIE activities

Public Participants - demographics and engagement

Participant engagement.

Workshop participants were paid £100 to participate by Ipsos Scotland.

To ensure that participants felt comfortable with the information and were willing to engage, an information session was held before the workshop to address key concepts and any initial areas of confusion. This was framed as a relaxed and collaborative session.

Workshop materials were produced by members of the team, and refined through collaboration with the full project team, as well as with Ipsos Scotland. This process was crucial in thinking through suitable language and topics in advance of the workshop discussions. These materials formed the backbone of discussions and were integral to the PIE workflow.

Participant feedback on the PIE activities.

The project team felt that participants were engaged during the process and in particular during the workshops. One key success was one of the participants joining an ongoing patient panel following the workshops.

Participant demographics - target and actual

Quota	Variable	Target recruits (of 40)	Actual recruits (of 39)
Age	16-24	6	6
	25-34	8	5
	35-54	13	12
	55+	13	16
Gender	Women	20	15
	Men	20	24
Location	Edinburgh	20	22
	Aberdeen	20	17
Ethnicity	Ethnic minorities	7	10
	White Scottish/British	33	29
Education level	Level 4 (degree, professional qualification)	12	16
	Level 3 (NHC / NHD or equivalent)	6	7
	Level 2 (Higher, A-Level or equivalent) and Level 1 (O Grade, Standard Grade or equivalent)	14	15
	No qualifications	8	1

The project team set targets for recruitment of participants, considering key demographic characteristics (seen above). Recruiting people to meet these targets was challenging, in particular it was difficult to attract people with 'no qualifications', and more participants with higher education levels were included shortly before the workshops started.

01: SARA - Project overview and PIE activities

Conclusions and next steps

In terms of data provenance, the SARA team is keen to take the tools developed and see how they work in other TREs. However, they do recognise that more evaluation is needed first. With regards to PIE beyond the DARE UK reporting, the SARA team is exploring avenues to share the learnings that were made possible through public consultation.

As well as news items through partner websites that will include the final public consultation report, **the SARA team is also investigating the merits of publishing a paper focused on the public consultation process within a journal such as the *International Journal of Population Data Science***. This publication will focus on how the contributions from public participants were directly incorporated into the project's outputs - a fairly novel outcome in the data science field. The aim will be to offer a case study on how this was achieved, providing an example for others.

In terms of SARA's commitment to PIE, the team will continue their attempts to secure additional funding and/or work collaboratively through other organisations, such as Research Data Scotland, to answer further important questions that will allow the evolution of data services with a clear social licence (mandate) to operate.

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There are obvious perceived risks around data privacy, and the idea of individual consent is of crucial importance in particular. For the future of TREs, when it comes to public perspectives, we need to ensure that we are doing the right things in the right ways.

Stuart Dunbar, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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Please click on the links to access the final reports: [SARA project report](#) | [SARA PIE report](#)

SACRO:

Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs

Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs was a collaboration involving the University of the West of England, University of Oxford, University of Edinburgh, University of Dundee, University of Aberdeen, Durham University, Research Data Scotland, Public Health Scotland, NHS Scotland, and Health Data Research UK.

SACRO: Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs

This project was about ensuring safe outputs of data in the final stage of releasing data to researchers. SACRO focused on the following key areas:

Consolidated framework – providing guidance for TREs to agree consistent, standard processes to assist in quality assurance.

Research outputs – designing and implementing a semi-automated system to aid human output checkers, reducing both the operating costs of TREs and the time taken to release research results.

The SACRO project will enable researchers to produce better and safer research.

Dr Jim Smith, Principal Investigator (PI)

02: SACRO - Project overview and PIE activities

Overview

According to the SACRO team, there is a clear opportunity to improve the way output checking happens within TREs. The vision of the SACRO project was to move some of this output checking earlier in the research process, allowing researchers to be more focused on checking outputs are safe.

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At present all outputs have to be manually checked, which creates a bottleneck in the system. We decided to address that bottleneck in a way that fits in with the future federated landscape of research across multiple TREs.

Dr Jim Smith, Principal Investigator (PI)

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The final check is the final part in making sure TREs are keeping data secure. There are lots of steps within the process to make sure data is not identifiable – this is the final, final check that is done by a machine AND a human.

Katie Oldfield, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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02: SACRO - Project overview and PIE activities

Listening to public opinion

Like all DARE UK funded projects, the SACRO project engaged with the public via a set of PIE activities. **The purpose of these activities was to gain public input on the consensus statement – one of the PIE outputs for SACRO.**

The project team accomplished this in close collaboration with the group Digital Critical Friends at OpenSAFELY from the Bennett Institute within Oxford University, alongside members of the public who sat on the SACRO steering group.

 Literature review – a literature review was performed by the SACRO team, focused on output checking and methods used, but also elements that would inform the output checking process alongside public perception. This was crucial in the SACRO project to ensure the project built upon existing information in this space.

 Online meetings – the SACRO team attended three online meetings with the Digital Critical Friends group to discuss the consensus statement and to enable open communication with the public. The group were sent drafts of the statement prior to the meeting, and the SACRO team were able to receive feedback on the output.

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The literature review was critical to the SACRO project. It meant we could draft consensus statements to test with the public which were informed by work that we did and existing literature.

Katie Oldfield, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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02: SACRO - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - process

A major success was the collaboration between the SACRO team and Digital Critical Friends - the public panel.

An online survey was shared with members of the public panel who participated in the activities. **The survey respondents said that their opinion was valued and the SACRO team did their best to action their recommendations.** The survey responses also indicated the participants' grasp of the project and its purpose:

- “Good opportunity to contribute to the discussion, share thoughts and influence the way forward in a safe, supportive and inclusive environment.”
- “Aside from the project’s influence on public trust, it will enable more studies on health research to be undertaken, potentially saving lives, by decreasing the operational costs of TREs and the time it takes to reveal research results.”

“*A major success of the project was our collaboration with Digital Critical Friends. The quality of involvement and engagement from the panel meant we were able to communicate in an understandable way.*

SACRO Team

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02: SACRO - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - impacts on the project

The PIE activities surfaced the following key learnings which have directly impacted the overall project:

- **Refinement of the draft consensus statement** - as stated, the main aim of the PIE activities within SACRO was to get public input into the draft consensus statement. This aim was met, with the consensus statement being updated as a direct result of the PIE activities.
- **Development of clearer project descriptions and visuals** - the public meetings were particularly useful for helping the SACRO team understand how to explain the project in a digestible manner. One outcome of this was a flow chart which helps convey the process in a visual way, and has been integrated into other project documents and outputs.

02: SACRO - Project overview and PIE activities

Public Participants - demographics and engagement

Participant engagement.

The SACRO project worked with an already established public group called the Digital Critical Friends at OpenSAFELY, through collaboration with the Bennett Institute in Oxford (www.bennett.ox.ac.uk). Members of this group were paid £25 an hour for their time.

At the time of writing this report, no information on the demographics of this group was available, but some concerns are noted as to whether it truly represents the views of the 'lay' public - largely due to the fact that it is an established group with a good understanding in this space.

Interactions with the group included discussions and feedback on draft work such as the consensus statement. The SACRO team also engaged an artist who produced a graphic report of a meeting to represent the discussion and key themes in a more attractive and accessible format.

Participant feedback on the PIE activities.

The project team noted that members of the group were very engaged and interested in the project. Panel managers provided similar feedback after the discussions. In addition, five members of the public gave detailed written feedback on the draft consensus statement - indicating continued engagement.

02: SACRO - Project overview and PIE activities

Conclusions and next steps

In terms of output checking, the SACRO team are hoping to see this tool embedded in most UK TREs over the next couple of years. Many TREs are seeing that this final step in the process can result in a 'bottleneck' that prevents researchers from accessing the data they need. The team believe SACRO can help relieve this 'bottleneck'.

With regards to PIE, the SACRO team is keen to maintain public engagement around TREs. With a view to being proactive in communicating to the public, they hope to continue to use these innovative projects to improve public awareness around TREs. They also hope that this project will improve acceptance of AI for public benefit in the future. **This project has created a support system which will help TREs throughout the UK – through improving awareness and acceptance of this tool amongst researchers. The team aim for this to be pivotal within the TRE space.**

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Communicating about TREs is not impossible – we can explain anything as long as we are creative and consistent about it.

Katie Oldfield, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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Through engagement with user groups, we have successfully developed eight principles for the use of automation within the TRE process – these have now been adopted by multiple data organisations and we hope these are used more over the coming years.

Dr Jim Smith, Principal Investigator (PI)

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Please click on the links to access the final reports: [SACRO project report](#) | [SACRO PIE report](#)

TELEPORT:

Connecting Researchers to Big Data at Light Speed

TELEPORT: Connecting Researchers to Big Data at Light Speed was a collaboration involving Swansea University, University of Edinburgh, and Public Health Scotland.

TELEPORT: Connecting Researchers to Big Data at Light Speed

This project aimed to revolutionise data access, allowing researchers to access and analyse data from multiple data environments under the concept of 'data federation' and a 'pop-up TRE'.

The project worked to produce the technical developments needed to join existing data providers and their analytical environments together, including two national TREs, to securely deliver 'federated access'.

TELEPORT can be considered part of 'the plumbing' for all the Phase 1 Driver Projects since it enables the efficient and secure interconnection of large datasets from multiple data providers.

Data federation is an invisible part – it's below the iceberg. People see the penguins on top of the iceberg having a nice time; they don't see the mass of ice underneath holding the whole thing up.

Professor Simon Thompson, Principal Investigator (PI)

Jargon buster

What is data federation?

Data federation is a technology that virtually unifies data from different sources and makes it accessible under a uniform access method.

What is federated access?

Federated access uses data federation technology to enable researchers to access multiple data environments simultaneously and analyse data using the concept of a single front door.

03: TELEPORT - Project overview and PIE activities

Overview

At the moment, when researchers have research questions which need data from many different places (such as running studies on the whole UK population), **a lot of work is involved in accessing each data environment, extracting what is needed, and then piecing those elements together in a way that can be used.** TELEPORT aims to revolutionise this process.

TELEPORT started the transformation of access to data across multiple TREs in the UK. Key to this transformation is a concept known as 'federated access'. This would allow researchers to access data housed in different digital and physical environments within a single virtual interconnected environment, without the need to move those data from their multiple host environments.

Essentially, through federated access, researchers can see all the data they need in one safe and secure online environment.

The technical developments produced by TELEPORT can join together existing data providers, through TREs, providing efficiencies for researchers to access data, and run studies to produce scientific outputs which have meaningful public benefit.

03: TELEPORT - Project overview and PIE activities

Listening to public opinion

The TELEPORT project engaged with the public via a set of PIE activities to include public perspectives on whether TELEPORT was generating public benefit in line with data security, safety, and best practice in health research.

We send a lot of projects to Consumer Panels; we are always asking their opinion.

Professor Simon Thompson, Principal Investigator (PI)

As a highly technical project, requiring background knowledge on the nature of TREs and the concept of data federation, TELEPORT involved existing panels and lay members with knowledge on the way TREs operate, and the concepts of data federation and federated access.

Appointing a TELEPORT Lay Lead – The Lay Lead acted as an advocate and public voice throughout project technical meetings. This helped communicate TELEPORT’s goals and public impacts appropriately to a lay audience and produced advocacy reports for the PIE panels to consider.

Public panels – The TELEPORT team attended a Consumer Panel meeting with the Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL) Databank. The Consumer Panel comprised more than a dozen members of the Welsh public who provided a gauge of the social acceptability of research using SAIL data. With the same aim, TELEPORT attended a meeting with HDR UK Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme, a UK-wide research driver programme that shares TELEPORT’s aims to streamline data research.

03: TELEPORT - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - process

Through the project's PIE activities, the TELEPORT team identified and addressed a key challenge:

 Technical terms – *TELEPORT is an extremely technical project and difficult by nature. However, the team was able to engage with relevant public groups to ensure that technical development was translated into real-world impact, plans, designs and deployments were described to gauge whether these were correctly shaped and suitable for public understanding.*

The team also made use of mature PIE groups to ensure the dissemination of information to already-recruited panels and discuss the developments of existing organisations' set-ups in more detail.

“ We are very happy with the PIE we have undertaken in terms of verifying and validating that our plans were in the public interest and there are perceived benefits to the work we have done.

TELEPORT Team

Through work with the public panels, it was made clear that members of the public welcome engagement with projects such as TELEPORT. Members had strong views on the public being consulted early, continuously, and more widely. While there were practical limitations to the PIE activities due to funding, this feedback was notable.

Following their contributions, members of the public were contacted to complete a survey. Due to GDPR restrictions, these results are not available to the TELEPORT team. This a learning for future projects to ensure that the outputs of surveys are accessible, and therefore beneficial.

03: TELEPORT - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - impacts on the project

The PIE activities surfaced the following key learnings which have directly impacted the overall project:

- **The concept and benefits of data federation are welcomed by the public –**
 - General feedback through PIE activities was that the TELEPORT project was a very good idea, and that anything making data access for science across the UK easier should be pursued.
- **The patient experience is key –**
 - Public participants highlighted that any systems created within TELEPORT should consider how to improve and enrich the patient experience, e.g., by providing more relevant insights and outputs concerning patient health.
- **Efficiency is clearly understood and welcomed by the public –**
 - Public participants quickly grasped that data federation offers efficiency which can have benefits in terms of cost and researcher time efficiency. Continuing to talk about these potential efficiencies will be important moving forwards.

It was valuable having a member of the public sitting in our meetings – they would occasionally raise a concern or question that made us think a little bit and realise we shouldn't make assumptions in that space.

Professor Simon Thompson, Principal Investigator (PI)

Public Participants - demographics and engagement

Participant engagement.

The TELEPORT team worked collaboratively with two existing panels/groups:

Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL) Databank Consumer Panel –

- This panel was made up of approximately 12 members of the Welsh public. No detailed demographic information is available and the project team noted this may bias PIE results.
- Panel members are offered an honorarium through a process in partnership with Health and Care Research Wales.

HDR UK Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme meeting –

- No detailed demographic information is available.
- No information regarding reimbursement is available.

To support discussions with these groups, the team developed briefing information which was compiled by 'less technical' members of the group and reviewed for refinements by governance and non-technical stakeholders from Swansea University, University of Edinburgh, and Public Health Scotland.

03: TELEPORT - Project overview and PIE activities

Conclusions and next steps

The TELEPORT team believe that the involvement of the public in TREs is very important. For the future, the team is focusing on enhancing collaboration between PIE efforts in different projects.

One goal is to move away from project-specific and relatively siloed PIE, towards programme-led collaborative PIE in which various projects work more closely together. This will enable projects to develop more cohesive messaging, disseminate information in a unified forum, create consensus, and standardise feedback.

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I'm really interested in the new world – not just the federation. How do we stand-up datasets in the future, so that the business model stacks up, is appropriate, and is available as universally as possible?

**Professor Simon Thompson,
Principal Investigator (PI)**

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It has been incredibly important to empower public groups in terms of them shaping how solutions such as TELEPORT fit into organisations, research, and science and provide checks and balances to ensure that the cyclical nature of research funding, development, and delivery is meaningful and benefits those who need the outputs the most – patients and the wider public.

TELEPORT Team

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Please click on the links to access the final reports: [TELEPORT project report](#) | [TELEPORT PIE report](#)

SATRE:

Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments

Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments was a collaboration involving the University of Dundee, Ulster University, University College London, Health Data Research UK, The Alan Turing Institute, and Research Data Scotland.

04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

SATRE: Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments

The SATRE project was about creating a consistent specification of capabilities for all TREs to follow in order to securely manage personal or sensitive data. The team focused on three key areas:

- **Engaging with the TRE community and the public** – to understand what works well (or not) in data research.
- **Identifying what it takes to build trust in a TRE** – both for the research community and for the wider society.
- **Being fully open and transparent throughout the project** – for the benefit of stakeholders and the public.

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Getting access to sensitive data is important for research for the public benefit. Researchers are conscious of how careful they need to be and TRE operators are keen to support safe, research use of data.

Dr Christian Cole, Principal Investigator (PI)

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04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

Overview

SATRE's goal was to create a consistent, high-standard specification of capabilities for all TREs to follow – considering the challenges surrounding sensitive data management and the attitudes, and needs of the public.

This specification of capabilities took the form of a comprehensive checklist for managers of TREs, aiming to improve consistency and ensure safe and secure access to shared data.

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Although it started as a more technical project, as SATRE progressed it expanded to include governance. Transparency of the work and operation of TREs is important in building public trust.

Katie Oldfield, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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Clarity can get lost in technical jargon which was why it was great to have public involvement at the heart of the project. It improved clarity and communication throughout the team.

Dr Christian Cole, Principal Investigator (PI)

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04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

Listening to public opinion

The SATRE project engaged with the public via a set of public involvement and engagement (PIE) activities.

- **Project involvement** – from as early as the proposal stage, two members of the public joined the project team. This approach was key, as the perspectives of these two team members helped shape all aspects of the project, including the PIE activities themselves, challenging the team to think carefully about how they communicate their activities to non-specialist audiences.
- **Workshops** – public workshops were developed and run with the involvement of the public members of the team. This gave workshop attendees the space and confidence to speak with ‘people like them’ about questions they had about TREs and the SATRE project. Two initial workshops explored the concept of trust in TREs and their architecture.
- **Follow-up** – while initial workshops were used to identify key principles for TRE specifications, follow-up public workshops gave an opportunity to reflect and respond to the earlier input, while also making sure the team had understood the public’s views correctly.

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There was a public voice challenging and collaborating with us throughout. How are we going to communicate that? How do we make it accessible? Members of the public brought a different perspective to the project.

Katie Oldfield, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - process

A major success, according to the SATRE team, was having two members of the public in the core project team and creating a welcoming and inclusive environment for their contributions.

We created an environment where people can give feedback – everyone on the SATRE team respected public views. We were initiated and nurtured by Dr Christian Cole, who created a 'platform' for the public's voice to be valued as much as everyone else's.

SATRE Team

The PIE activities identified two key challenges which the SATRE team was able to face and mitigate.

 Public engagement – SATRE is a broad data infrastructure project about how TREs are set-up and managed. Some knowledge was required before the team were able to start talking about the project to the public. The SATRE team worked hard to establish a good knowledge-base about TREs, before they started asking questions and getting input from members of the public. Challenges also arose in the recruiting and delivering of in-person sessions.

 Technical aspects – the use of GitHub for interacting with other work packages was an initial hurdle. This was a new tool for the members of the public on the team and the PIE lead to use, and therefore required some upskilling.

04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - impacts on the project

The initial PIE workshops identified four key themes which people cared about in terms of trust in TREs:

Cybersecurity

Oversight

Data de-identification

Transparency

These themes helped shape the plan for the TRE specification. An online survey was later shared with members of the public panel who participated in the activities. Survey respondents felt that their opinion was valued:

- “Almost every meeting changed the way they did things because of my and other public members’ contributions.”
- “I was very vocal and listened to. I helped design and develop the public involvement and we adapted it as and when we needed to.”

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As researchers, we have to be guided by the public to do our best.

Dr Christian Cole, Principal Investigator (PI)

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In follow-up workshops, further changes were incorporated in the final stages of the project, including:

- Upgrading of the Public Involvement and Engagement statements from optional to mandatory.
- Inclusion of a statement for TREs to publicly report on near misses and incidents of data breach.
- Detail added on the level of information TREs should include on their website about data policies.

04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

Public Participants - demographics and engagement

Participant engagement.

Public participants were from a mix of UK countries. The SATRE project did not collect any data on participant demographics, beyond noting their home country and previous experience of data projects (in some circumstances).

Participants received £50 retail vouchers for participating in a session.

Engagement with the sessions was mixed. The project team noted that while some sessions were fully recruited, others were under subscribed. Some sessions were in-person and others were virtual and engagement during these sessions varied by participant.

The project team created a bespoke PIE presentation for these sessions, including points to encourage questions and discussion. The team collected data on this presentation after the sessions and used this for refinement.

Importantly, the SATRE project included two members of the public embedded in the project team.

Participant feedback on the PIE activities.

The embedded members of the public provided positive feedback, noting they felt their input was taken on board and influenced the project. No feedback is available for the specific sessions.

04: SATRE - Project overview and PIE activities

Conclusions and next steps

The SATRE team is focusing on two major next steps. The first is ensuring that PIE is built into future iterations of the project; the second is evaluating how TRES interpret the language and content of the published specification, as they begin to evaluate themselves against it.

The team recommends that, as the SATRE specification is taken forward, **ongoing public engagement should be budgeted and built-in so that public input into SATRE guidelines are included as a rule.**

“

The majority of the public have no idea their health information is being sent to a database for use for research. I think they would be happy with this as long they were assured it is safe, anonymised and would make a difference to the nation's health.

Survey Respondent

”

“

Being on the inside, I can see there is huge potential and benefit for the public in this work. However, this message is not being translated well to the public. Getting more members of the public involved in this type of work is helping researchers not repeat the same mistakes previously made.

Dr Christian Cole, Principal Investigator (PI)

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Please click on the links to access the final reports: [SATRE project report](#) | [SATRE PIE report](#)

TRE-FX:

Delivering a Federated Network of Trusted Research Environments to Enable Safe Data Analytics

Trusted Research Environments – Federated Analytics (TRE-FX) was a collaboration involving The University of Manchester, University of Nottingham, University of Dundee, University of Swansea, University of Birmingham, Health Data Research UK (HDR UK), University of Liverpool, Bitfount, and the Birmingham University Hospitals NHS Trust.

05: TRE-FX - Project overview and PIE activities

TRE-FX: Delivering a Federated Network of Trusted Research Environments to Enable Safe Data Analytics

TRE-FX aimed to show how we could revolutionise analysis and data exchange for existing TRE data providers, and analysis toolkits by streamlining the plumbing needed.

Already available tools and technologies, such as research objects and workflow execution platforms, can be brought together to make a standardised mechanism for analyses to be performed across TREs, while supporting the Five Safes principles that govern and protect sensitive data.

“

We should be able to use all data available to answer our research questions, not just the ones that we can access locally. By standardising the technology, we can help standardise how we support Five Safes governance – this project is about helping support compliance by default.

Professor Carole Goble, Principal Investigator (PI)

”

05: TRE-FX - Project overview and PIE activities

Overview

Right now, it is hard for researchers to perform an analysis that involves asking research questions of data that sit across multiple TREs.

TRE-FX developed technical infrastructure that assists the communication and information exchange between TREs that host securely held data, and popular analysis toolkits such as DataSHIELD and BitFount. They created a framework for easy and secure information exchange supporting advancements in health research.

TRE-FX looked to solve the problems that arise in the absence of standardisation of data access and access mechanisms between different TREs. The team developed and deployed secure software programmes that assist the communication and information exchange between TREs that host administrative data, hospital data or any other data that must be securely held. By doing so, they created a framework for easy and secure information exchange in data research, supporting advancements in health research.

The TRE-FX team collaborated with an on-site/local TRE and two cloud-based TREs, adding to technologies that have already been developed by ELIXIR and HDR-UK. **The collaboration was to prove that this can be adopted by pre-existing TRE installations without compromising the Five Safes principles, and delivered in line with the appropriate security and governance controls.**

05: TRE-FX - Project overview and PIE activities

Listening to public opinion

The TRE-FX project engaged with the public via a set of public involvement and engagement (PIE) activities to build a picture of public insights and concerns surrounding topics such as data security, federated analytics, and personal data usage.

 Workshops – a total of 40 members of the public participated in two workshops and focus group discussions facilitated by Alterline, an insight and intelligence agency.

 Accessible information materials – in order to ensure that members of the public were well informed on relevant topics such as federated data and the Five Safes (see page 39), explanatory materials, including videos, were created. This meant that contributors were familiar with the intricacies of the topics when providing their insights and concerns. To view these materials yourself please click the link [here](#).

This interaction with the public directly influenced project outcomes, confirmed the importance of remaining sensitive to feedback, and ultimately assisted in ensuring that the TRE-FX project resonated with its intended audience, with its outputs aligned to their expectations and concerns.

“

There are people that are less comfortable with data sharing – we know that there are certain groups that are more nervous about this. With that in mind we were able to engage with the public and lay some of those issues to rest in this project – and that is really important.

Suzy Gallier, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

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05: TRE-FX - Project overview and PIE activities

PIE learnings - process

The TRE-FX team noted the following process learnings from their PIE activities:

- **Importance of communications materials** – although participants came to the panel with limited comprehension of federated analytics, the public-facing materials developed by the team managed to bridge this knowledge gap with notable improvement in understanding.
- **Focus on transparency** – the emphasis on transparent communication around data usage, the availability of opt-in and opt-out choices, and the sharing of success stories were received positively at the PIE activities. Additionally, the introduction of the Five Safes (see page 39) framework was recognised as beneficial, though suggestions for further enhancements were made.

Following their contributions, TRE-FX contacted the members of the public to complete a survey. Due to GDPR restrictions, these results are not available to the TRE-FX team. This is a learning for future projects to ensure that the outputs of surveys are accessible and therefore beneficial.

“

What we learned from the public is that all this needs to be transparent. What we do is simplify interaction with TREs and expose that interaction so you can see what is happening so that we can be trusted.

Professor Carole Goble, Principal Investigator (PI)

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PIE learnings - impacts on the project

The PIE activities surfaced the following key learnings which have directly impacted the overall project:

The public participants saw clear value in the work of TRE-FX:

- The potential advantages of federated analytics, such as fostering research collaboration, integrating diverse data sources, and enhancing research outcomes, were well-understood and appreciated by the public.

The management of data needs to be underpinned by transparency:

- Participants raised issues such as distinguishing between research and commercial utilisation, complying with data privacy norms, and ensuring that data is used solely for genuine research endeavours. They highlighted the importance of clarifying the specific details of data usage, including intended use, entities accessing data, retention periods of data, and associated security measures.

Trust is the backbone to all projects of this nature:

- Trust emerged as a pivotal factor for the public. Participants expressed the necessity for external regulatory mechanisms to guarantee data security and deter unauthorised access. To mitigate this concern, trust can be promoted by encouraging systems of accountability, such as external oversight measures and possibly the involvement of independent bodies to guarantee data protection and sanction any misconduct.

05: TRE-FX - Project overview and PIE activities

Public Participants - demographics and engagement

Participant engagement.

The demographics of workshop attendees were captured and are presented here. These data highlight that there was space for improved representation amongst public participants, e.g., with better representation of non-white ethnicities.

The TRE-FX team put a lot of focus on their PIE informational materials. This included testing, feedback, and refinement. The team also co-created some content with members of the public, inviting them to help draft text for video scripts and brochures.

Participant feedback on the PIE activities.

The project team felt that within the scope of TRE-FX, the feedback from PIE attendees was overwhelmingly positive. Both the interactive workshops and focus group discussions witnessed active participation and yielded valuable input.

Education

Ethnicity

Sex

Location

Work Status

Age

05: TRE-FX - Project overview and PIE activities

Conclusions and next steps

The TRE-FX team is focusing on future research to explore the opportunities and address the challenges associated with federated analytics.

Incorporating the insights from the PIE activities, the team also aims to promote clearer understanding of the project's potential in advancing health outcomes.

“

There's still a lot of work to do and there's a large piece of public education that needs to happen. There is a national need for explaining data better to everybody, particularly as we are moving in a digital age and safety and security is important.

Suzy Gallier, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

”

“

While the TRE-FX initiative successfully elucidated the tenets and advantages of Federated Analytics to the participants, it also brought to the forefront certain reservations and concerns, underscoring the need for continuous dialogue, improvements in data security, and heightened transparency in operations.

TRE-FX Team

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Please click on the links to access the final reports: [TRE-FX project report](#) | [TRE-FX PIE report](#)

Summary

DARE UK PIE Report Summary

The five DARE UK Driver Projects aimed to revolutionise the way we process, manage, and release results from research on potentially sensitive data, such as personal health data. The projects tackle various aspects of data management, with the shared goal of making it easier and more efficient for researchers to access sensitive data while upholding principles of data security and privacy.

Because these projects were focused on sensitive personal data, it was essential that the research teams liaised with members of the public to understand their perspectives and concerns.

Through PIE activities, each project was able to better understand the perspectives and concerns of the public with regards to TREs and the management of sensitive data. This has generated insights and ideas which helped to shape the direction of their work.

Though the PIE activities were slightly different for each project, **several core themes emerged across projects: the importance of transparency, education about technical terms, accessibility of information, and the continuation of outreach and public involvement activities, as the projects evolve.**

Reflections

Key learnings and recommendations from the perspective of the Phase 1 Driver Projects

The teams behind the Phase 1 Driver Projects have all embraced PIE activities and the projects themselves have benefitted from public input. The teams have reflected on their key learnings and recommendations which have been summarised across all Phase 1 Driver Projects.

Key learnings and recommendations

Resources
and planning

Roles and
responsibilities

A culture of
open discussion

Testing
and refinement

Tracking and
recording PIE activities

Resources and planning

Key learnings

- PIE activities are valuable but require dedicated resources and focus to be planned and executed as well as possible.
- PIE activities are most effective when integrated with the overall project plan, with key milestones for public feedback which come at suitable times for project refinement. In addition, different types of PIE activities may have varying impacts at different time points in a project, e.g., a discussion-based workshop may have more value at the start of a project than at the end, while a survey may be more beneficial at the end of a project to capture final refinements and reflection.

Recommendations

- Have a dedicated PIE Lead integrated into the project team, where possible. Consider recruiting a member of the public who has prior experience participating in PIE activities to play this role. There is also benefit in working with an inexperienced public member, as they can offer more representative public perspectives.
- Develop a detailed project timeline which fully integrates PIE activities with the wider project and highlights timepoints where PIE insights can help shape the next stage of project development.
- Consider what types of PIE activity have the greatest value at different time points of the project.

Key learnings and recommendations

Resources
and planning

**Roles and
responsibilities**

A culture of
open discussion

Testing
and refinement

Tracking and
recording PIE activities

Roles and responsibilities

Key learnings

- Once projects are up and running and PIE activities ongoing, lots of individual tasks emerge, e.g., coordinating public meetings, developing materials for meetings, and defining contracting and reimbursement processes. It is important to assign these tasks clearly throughout the team and PIE lead (if present).

Recommendations

- When planning and integrating PIE activities, develop a roles and responsibilities matrix, e.g., RACI (**R**esponsible, **A**ccountable, **C**onsulted, **I**nformed) which helps all team members understand their contribution to the PIE workflows.
- Consider having a recurring scheduled meeting dedicated to PIE activities and use this to recap and review ongoing tasks and responsibilities.

Key learnings and recommendations

Resources
and planning

Roles and
responsibilities

**A culture of
open discussion**

Testing
and refinement

Tracking and
recording PIE activities

A culture of open discussion

Key learnings

- Culturally it is essential to be open to challenging questions and feedback. This enhances the impact of PIE activities and improves interactions with members of the public.

Recommendations

- Culture comes from everyone – it is important to encourage all team members to contribute to a culture of open discussion, and protect time to reflect on this as the project progresses.
- Assign a dedicated project leader to be responsible for building and maintaining this culture.

Key learnings and recommendations

Resources
and planning

Roles and
responsibilities

A culture of
open discussion

**Testing
and refinement**

Tracking and
recording PIE activities

Testing and refinement

Key learnings

- When communicating complicated research and scientific concepts, creating simple visual materials for a public audience is helpful. These materials should be treated as evolving documents, which are subject to continuous improvements and refinements.

Recommendations

- Consider what materials you need to communicate your project within PIE activities early on.
- Develop a set of iterative materials which can be used throughout PIE activities, and manage these as shared and evolving documents which can help centralise and process PIE inputs and improvements.

Key learnings and recommendations

Resources
and planning

Roles and
responsibilities

A culture of
open discussion

Testing
and refinement

**Tracking and
recording PIE activities**

Tracking and recording PIE activities

Key learnings

- It is important to track PIE activities as much as possible, including metrics such as engagement, attendance, drop-outs, frequently asked questions etc.
- It is essential to ensure that groups formed by members of the public represent the diversity of the public as much as possible, considering factors such as education, gender and ethnicity.
- Tracking of PIE activities may include additional stakeholders, e.g., Ipsos Scotland. Where this happens, it is important to be clear what data you will have access to regarding your participants, and integrate this into your tracking and recording processes. If data is unavailable, e.g., due to privacy regulations, record this in your tracker.

Recommendations

- Set out what you are going to measure in terms of PIE effectiveness at the start of the project. These can be framed as 'key performance indicators' (KPIs). Create a document which serves to capture KPI data throughout PIE activities and return to this document when asked to report on PIE effectiveness.
- Be focused about what you want to measure and why. Connect these intended KPIs back to any funding reporting requirements. Can you capture one KPI which demonstrates the overall success of your PIE activities?
- Include processes and documents to track and record demographic and engagement information about your public participants.

Reflections

Key learnings from the perspective of DARE UK

As the administrator of research funding for the Phase 1 Driver Projects, DARE UK plays an important role in supporting effective PIE activities, as well as learning from what went well and what could have been done better in the context of each project's PIE workflows.

Ultimately, this enables DARE UK to be a more constructive and active partner in project PIE activities in the future, leading to better public engagement, clearer outcomes, and greater public benefit.

Key learnings

Supporting project teams to embrace PIE from the start

Sharing learnings from previous projects and across active projects

PIE planning, processes, and participant continuity

Offering ongoing expertise and input

Supporting project teams to embrace PIE from the start

Key learnings

- While most research teams acknowledge the value of PIE activities in their work, there is still room for all stakeholders to embrace this more fully, both in terms of planning, culture, transparency, and reflecting on the learnings from PIE and how these might impact their work.

Future learnings for DARE UK

- With future projects, DARE UK would be a more active partner in PIE facilitation, offering expertise, support, connections, and templates to newly funded project teams, to ensure that their PIE activities are delivered in line with established best practices.
- With future projects, DARE UK would consider hosting educational sessions with project teams at the start of newly funded projects. These would include case studies which demonstrate the value of PIE activities, as well as top tips on how to embrace PIE in terms of team culture, processes, and planning.
- With future projects, DARE UK would provide clear guidance and templates for what project teams are expected to track and report in terms of PIE activities.

Key learnings

Supporting project teams to embrace PIE from the start

Sharing learnings from previous projects and across active projects

PIE planning, processes, and participant continuity

Offering ongoing expertise and input

Sharing learnings from previous projects and across active projects

Key learnings

- There is no one size fits all for PIE activities, some are online, some are in-person, and others are simply questionnaires. In addition, many challenges are practical ones, such as being unclear how to reimburse members of the public for their time, or not being able to recontact people who attended a workshop for their feedback at a later date.

Future learnings for DARE UK

- With future projects, DARE UK would consider mechanisms to share 'best practice examples' of PIE activities with newly funded project teams. This 'best practice examples' resource would cover common challenges, such as how members of the public were reimbursed and engaged across multiple touchpoints, e.g., workshops followed by surveys.

Key learnings

Supporting project teams to embrace PIE from the start

Sharing learnings from previous projects and across active projects

PIE planning, processes, and participant continuity

Offering ongoing expertise and input

PIE planning, processes, and participant continuity

Key learnings

- Ideally, PIE activities would be considered and planned into the core flow of research projects from the start. In reality, PIE activities are often ‘bolted-on’ to existing plans, and while this still adds value, it creates the risk that projects are not at suitable phases to respond to public input. In addition, it can make it hard to create continuity across a project life cycle, e.g., the outcomes of one workshop would ideally flow into the next workshop, and this may mean that these sessions benefit from the same attendance, but this requires planning, continuity, and ongoing contact with the contributing members of the public.
- Project teams have a lot to focus on, and PIE activities add to their workload. DARE UK has a role to play in ensuring project teams have the adequate time and resources needed to fully plan and execute effective PIE activities, as well as report the success of those activities to funders.

Future learnings for DARE UK

- With future projects, DARE UK would consider developing a set of project templates which support planning and continuity. Examples of these would be ‘participant engagement letters’, ‘post-workshop surveys’, and ‘tracking sheets’ to map participant demographics.
- With future projects, DARE UK would ensure all project teams are clear on the timelines and requirements for reporting the effectiveness of PIE activities to funders. This would include challenging timelines where not realistic and working with project teams to argue for more resources where needed.

Key learnings

Supporting project teams to embrace PIE from the start

Sharing learnings from previous projects and across active projects

PIE planning, processes, and participant continuity

Offering ongoing expertise and input

Offering ongoing expertise and input

Key learnings

- Executing PIE activities within the context of a research project is challenging. Researchers are typically highly specialised in their field, and PIE activities draw on experience and skillsets more aligned with communications professionals. In most research teams, there is value which can be added by people with these skill sets, either as dedicated PIE leads, or on an *ad hoc* basis.

Future learnings for DARE UK

- With future projects, DARE UK would consider giving project teams access to expertise and advice from PIE professionals who could help them reflect on and refine their PIE activities to get the most from their time with the public.
- With future projects, DARE UK would consider facilitating connections between project teams and external organisations who can support PIE expertise, e.g., PEDRI (Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative).

How 'semi' is semi-automation?

Semi-automation is the combination of automatic processes and human input or checks. Different parts of the process in the SARA project have varying amounts of automation; for example, data provenance is largely automated, but the handling of free-text is done by a human. The core idea is that the automated parts of a semi-automated process help to check large amounts of data, but the human factor remains key, particularly for sensitive steps.

As a Natural Language Processing (NLP) practitioner, I believe that it would be incredibly difficult to build a system that would automatically and reliably remove sensitive information in all scenarios.

Dr Arlene Casey, Principal Investigator (PI)

The PIE workshops confirmed that 'automation' is one of the main concerns for the public, with human involvement being perceived as positive: a sensible 'human' decision is being made. These workshops also made it clear that the public understands the topics of 'data ownership', and 'data extraction'. On the other side of the argument, semi-automation can help remove human-driven bias, but this discussion continues, and there is some work remaining to convince the public of the trustworthiness of semi-automated processes.

The Five Safes Principles

The Five Safes framework is a set of principles developed in the 2010s, aimed at enabling data services to provide safe research access to data. The Five Safes principles have been adopted by the large majority of TREs across the UK. The framework has become best practice in data protection whilst fulfilling the demands of open science and transparency, and has enabled UK TREs to provide approved researchers with controlled access to sensitive or confidential data. With this approach, researchers can access and use datasets in a secure and responsible way.

Security in our data is vital coupled with the ability to utilise data in an appropriate way.

Suzy Gallier, Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) Lead

The Five Safes

- **Safe data:** data is treated to protect any confidentiality concerns.
- **Safe projects:** research projects are approved by data owners for the public good.
- **Safe people:** researchers are trained and authorised to use data safely.
- **Safe settings:** a secure environment which prevents unauthorised use.
- **Safe outputs:** screened and approved outputs that are non-disclosive.

